

TRANSVERSE DOPPLER CURRENT PROFILERS

Thomas L. Clarke

Ocean Acoustics Division/AOML/NOAA
Miami, Florida 33149

Abstract

A new type of doppler acoustic current profiler (DCP) based on the transverse doppler principle is presented. A transverse DCP measures velocity perpendicular to an acoustic beam by measuring the differential doppler shift between the outputs of two or more receiving transducers using coherent processing. The governing equations for a transverse DCP are presented and the procedure for designing a transverse DCP is outlined. Results from operating a prototype transverse DCP system in Chesapeake Bay adjacent to a main shipping channel and in the Bear Cut channel near the port of Miami are discussed. Possible applications of transverse DCP systems include monitoring of water flow in shipping channels as well as oceanographic measurement.

1. Introduction

Conventional doppler acoustic current profilers (DCP) employ a single transducer to sample the acoustic return from scattering objects which have been illuminated by another (or possibly the same) acoustic transducer. Denoting the speed of sound by c , the velocity component of the scattering object(s) in the direction of the illuminating transducer by v , and letting ϕ be the angle between the illuminating transducer and the sampling transducer as viewed from the scattering object, the doppler shift is given by

$$\Delta f = \frac{2v}{c} f_0 \cos \phi. \quad (1)$$

The quantity f_0 is the frequency of the illuminating sound. In case the same transducer is used for illumination and for sampling, $\phi = 0$ so that $\cos \phi$ term in equation (1) equals one. Also, if $c = 1500$ m/sec is used, then the constant $2/c$ has the value 13.3 Hz/cm/sec/MHz. That is, with $f_0 = 1$ MHz, the doppler shift Δf is 13.3 Hz per centimeter per second of water velocity.

Unfortunately, it is not easy to arrange favorable conditions for the measurement of the frequency shift, Δf , while at the same time retaining the advantages of acoustic measurement such as separation of the measuring instrument from the region being measured, and the ability to remotely sense a large volume of water. The usual solution to the problem of defining the sampling volume is to use a narrow conical beam and to broadcast the illuminating sound in pulses. This permits a volume of water defined by the width of the acoustic beam and of length $c\tau/2$ where τ is the pulse length to be defined. When this technique is used, the illuminating and sampling transducers are often physically identical. Note also that this technique lends itself well to remote sensing. Provided sufficient signal is scattered from the sampling volume, there is no limitation on how far from the (common) transducer the sampled volume may be. The width of the sample volume grows with range,

however, so that unless the beam is very narrow, the sampled volume may become undesirably large at long range.

The chief difficulty with this repetitive pulse method is with measurement of the frequency shift, Δf . The ideally continuous acoustic return is now multiplied by a window of length τ repeated at the pulse repetition rate f_s . The approach taken in most previous DCP's that use the pulse technique is to consider the return from each pulse as a time series by itself [1]. This short time series is then analyzed to extract the doppler shift. Unfortunately, this single pulse method of estimating the doppler shift has great limitations, as will be seen.

The nature of the sound scatterers is of great importance for doppler because the variability of the scatterers determines the pulse to pulse variability of the return from the sample volume, and their physical nature determines their dispersive effect on the various frequency components in the transmitted illuminating sound pulse. The scatterers also cause variability when they move within the sample volume randomly from pulse to pulse as will happen with particulate scatterers in a turbulent fluid or with freely moving planktonic scatterers. In this case the cloud of scatterers acts like a "diffraction grating" so that the many frequency components in the transmitted pulse are reflected with randomized phases. A transmitted pulse is always associated with sideband frequencies produced by the pulse modulation process, and when the phases of these sideband frequencies are randomized by a cloud of scatterers, the result can be very unlike the transmitted pulse.

Figure 1. Cloud of scatterers in random motion, corresponding doppler spectrum and typical signal return.

Figure 1 shows a cloud of scatterers each moving with a small random velocity about the mean. Each scatterer contributes a single doppler shifted component to the acoustic return, indicated by the arrows in the spectrum. When many scatterers are averaged over many pulses the result is the continuous spectrum with mean $\bar{f} = f_0 + \Delta f$ indicated by the dashed line. This is the doppler spectrum, which for passive scatterers is an indication of the turbulence level [2]. Below the spectrum in Figure 1 is a typical time series of the acoustic return from the cloud of scatterers having that doppler spectrum. This signal is very unlike a sinusoid with frequency \bar{f} , and the difficulty for the single pulse method of doppler processing is to estimate \bar{f} from a short sample of this time series.

Without going into the fundamentals of signal processing theory, performance limitations for single pulse doppler systems can be deduced from well-known relations. The relationship between the uncertainty of the frequency of a signal (measurement error of the doppler shift) and the measurement time (τ for a single pulse system) given by

$$\delta f \tau \approx 1 \quad (2)$$

when $1/\tau$, the transmitted bandwidth, is much greater than the doppler spectrum width. Those familiar with quantum mechanics will recognize a similarity to the Heisenberg uncertainty principle. Equation (2) is of similar fundamental importance in signal processing, and sets fundamental limits to measurement that cannot be exceeded. To the electronically minded, measurement schemes occur that seem to readily improve on the relation in equation (2). Closer analysis of these methods show that they depend upon knowledge of the signal (e.g., the signal is a near perfect sine wave etc.) that cannot be assumed for a pulsed signal whose phase has been randomized.

Substituting the relation $\Delta R = c\tau/2$ into the uncertainty relation, equation (2), and using equation (1) one has

$$\Delta R \Delta v \approx c^2/f_0 \ 4 \cos \phi \quad (3)$$

as the relationship between the measurement error of velocity, Δv , and the length of the sample volume, ΔR . The constant multiplying $1/f_0$ in equation (3) has the value 56 m cm/sec MHz. Thus, at 1 MHz a range cell length of 1 meter is accompanied by a velocity uncertainty of 56 cm/sec. Averaging many measurements only slowly improves the estimate because the velocity measurements obtained from analyzing individual pulses are statistically independent. Thus, averaging 100 measurements reduces the error by a factor of only ten, so that the uncertainty in the velocity measurement is still 5.6 cm/sec for a range cell of 1m at 1 MHz.

Another method of extracting doppler information from a pulsed acoustic system is pulse to pulse coherent processing. Coherent processing involves looking at the change in phase of the return signal from pulse to pulse; since the frequency is the derivative of phase, this gives an estimate of the doppler shift of the signal. This method of processing is common in doppler radar but is rarely applied to sonar. Recently, this method has been applied by Lhermitte [2] to produce a DCP.

As with a single pulse system, a series of pulses is transmitted. Instead of processing each pulse as a subseries of the full time series, a new time series is synthesized from samples taken at the desired range once per transmitted pulse. A fundamental limitation here is set by the sampling theorem. Since the signal is sampled at the pulse rate, f_s , the sampling theorem requires that

$$f_s \geq \Delta f_{\max}/2 \quad (4)$$

where Δf_{\max} is the doppler shift corresponding to the maximum water velocity v_{\max} expected. The sampling theorem, equation (4), can be interpreted as setting a lower bound on the pulse frequency, or through the two-way travel time relation, on the maximum range. That is,

$$R_{\max} v_{\max} \leq c^2/f_0 \ 2 \cos \phi \quad (5)$$

Note the similarity to the limits for the single pulse processing system given by equation (3). The numerical constants are even identical to within a factor of two. Note, however, that there is no limitation on the length of the synthesized time series, so that there is no limit to the theoretical accuracy of measurement using the pulse coherent system.

Figure 2 illustrates the difference between single pulse processing and pulse to pulse coherent processing. The top time series shows a series of pulses (vertical arrows) which give the signals that follow. These signals have been converted to base band, that is the frequency component f_0 has been removed, so that the frequency of the signals is the doppler shift Δf . The pulse windowing process is indicated by the dotted lines leading to the short time series of length ΔR below the full time series of signal. It is the task of the signal processor to extract the doppler shift, Δf , from this short piece of time series as indicated by the double arrow. As shown above the uncertainty relation for time series produces fundamental limitations in the accuracy to which Δf and hence Δv can be measured by this method.

Figure 2. Sampling schemes of single pulse doppler (top) and pulse to pulse doppler (bottom).

Note however, that there is no limitation on the time between pulses as indicated by the broken lines between the pulses. Thus, a single pulse doppler system can sample to as distant a range as signal strength considerations allow. The pulse to pulse coherent system is indicated in the same way on the bottom of Figure 2. As before, a series of pulses (arrows) is transmitted and the indicated signals are received. Instead of processing a subseries of the

full time series, a new time series is synthesized by sampling the original time series once per transmitted pulse as indicated by the dotted lines. Note, that there is no limitation on the length of the time series as indicated by the broken lines in the lower part of Figure 2 so that there is no limit to the theoretical accuracy of measurement using the pulse coherent system.

The curious relation between the limitations of the single pulse system, equation (3), and the limitations of the pulse to pulse coherent system, equation (5), shows that there is no simple way to combine the two systems to overcome the limitations of both. One might think to use the pulse coherent system as a vernier on the coarse measurement provided by a single pulse system. But since there is no overlap between the limits of the two systems this is not possible.

There exist sophisticated methods using psuedo-random [3] codes to modulate the signal that combine the properties of the single pulse system and the pulse to pulse coherent system. These psuedo-random techniques are fairly common in sophisticated radar systems, but they require extremely complex electronics to implement. There are also difficult tradeoffs between range and velocity ambiguity (pulse to pulse coherent doppler's problem) and susceptibility to spurious returns. Single pulse systems are in susceptible to spurious returns (multiples) in range, but the psuedo-random technique introduces the possibility of spurious returns in velocity; that is, a strong scatter at one velocity may show up at another velocity. It is thus unlikely that a useful oceanographic instrument might be based upon psuedo-random techniques.

2. Transverse Doppler Operation

Many of the limitations identified in the previous section can be eliminated by utilizing a special transducer geometry that enables the measurement of the doppler shift transverse to the illuminating beam. A single narrow beamwidth transducer transmits a pulse of sound that is sensed by auxiliary broadband transducers as shown in Figure 3. At any given time the signal sensed by the auxiliary transducers is from a volume determined by the width of the main beam and by the length of the pulse. This beam geometry is often used in laser velocimetry [4]. Note also that the Fourier transform relation between spectra and correlation functions transforms a transverse doppler system into something like a correlation sonar [5].

Figure 3. Schematic diagram of operation of transverse doppler current profiler.

The main beam transmits frequency f_0 and the auxiliary transducers subtend an angle 2θ as seen by the scatterers in the sampling volume. The transverse doppler shift is defined in the processor as the difference in received frequencies at the two auxiliary transducers, i.e., the differential doppler shift. Defining v_T as the velocity transverse to the main beam, analysis shows that

$$\Delta f_T = f_I - f_{II} = \frac{2v_T}{c} f_0 \sin \theta \quad (6)$$

The transverse doppler shift thus has the same relation to the transverse velocity component as the radial doppler shift has to the radial velocity component except that $\cos \phi$ is replaced by $\sin \theta$. This slight change results in a great improvement in DCP system performance tradeoffs.

For useful remote sensing geometries the angle θ will be fairly small, on the order of a few degrees. The transverse doppler shift will thus be at least an order of magnitude smaller than the radial doppler shift. This exacerbates the problem of single pulse processing, but improves the situation with pulse to pulse coherent processing. To see this, the limitations for the transverse doppler become

$$\Delta v_T \Delta R \approx c^2 / f_0^4 \sin \theta \quad (7)$$

and

$$v_{Tmax} R_{max} \leq c^2 / f_0^2 \sin \theta \quad (8)$$

That is, the limitations are of the same form as for radial doppler with $\sin \theta$ replacing $\cos \phi$.

Equation (7) says that when θ is small the error in the transverse doppler will be much larger than the error in the radial doppler for comparable geometries. On the other hand, equation (8) shows that when using the transverse doppler shift, the maximum range can be extended, or the maximum measurable velocity can be increased or some combination of the two. The method of processing of choice for transverse doppler is thus pulse to pulse coherent processing. A system combining the transducer geometry shown in Figure 3 together with pulse to pulse coherent processing as shown in Figure 2 will thus have very desirable characteristics for use as a profiling doppler current meter. By varying the angle θ the coefficient relating doppler frequency shift to water velocity can be varied over a wide range for a given frequency f_0 . This will permit the maximum range/maximum velocity tradeoff given by equation (8) to be tailored to the specific application. Four examples are:

- (1) For assessing the effect of water flow on sediment transport very detailed information about the boundary layer within a few meters of the ocean bottom is required. This information ideally consists of profiles of velocity with rapid time resolution and detailed spatial resolution (a few centimeters). A system utilizing the transverse doppler principle with $f_0 = 3$ MHz, and $\theta = 2^\circ$ will have a maximum velocity of 107 cm/sec for a maximum range of 2.5 meters. The pulse rate f_s will be 300 Hz so that response will be rapid and the range resolution can easily be in the centimeter range. In addition, 3 MHz is a good frequency for sensing suspended sand within the boundary layer, and the signal can be additionally processed to recover the radial

doppler signal. Thus, the instrument would be a full three axis profiling current meter/concentration sensor without flow interaction. All profiling acoustic current meters have the capability of providing profiles of suspended material concentration. The type of suspended material to which a particular system is most sensitive will, of course, depend on the system frequency and the environment.

- (2) Flux measurements in estuary inlets require simultaneous measurement of profiles of velocity and suspended material. A transverse acoustic doppler system is ideal for this application also. In this case, the choice $f_0 = 1$ MHz and $\theta = .5^\circ$ gives a maximum velocity of 161 cm/sec with a maximum range of 20 meters. The frequency 1 MHz will be reasonably sensitive to the type of suspended material expected in an estuarine environment.
- (3) A system designed for monitoring current in a harbor might require a longer range capability than an estuarine research instrument. The system may have to be located at the edge of a channel and look across the channel at an angle in order to observe the current within the channel without interfering with shipping. Maximum velocities may also be large due to the discharge of rivers into the harbor. A system using $f_0 = 200$ KHz and $\theta = .5^\circ$ satisfies these requirements with a range of 50 meters and maximum velocity of 322 cm/sec.
- (4) A system for measuring profiles of water velocity on the outer continental shelf or under ocean current such as the Gulf Stream would require a large maximum range and a large maximum current. In order to satisfy these requirements the lowest frequency that significantly scatters from the largest passively floating scatterers must be used. These scatterers are zooplankton which, while free swimming, swim only slowly and the frequency is 20 KHz. Reducing θ to $.25^\circ$ results in a maximum range of 750 meters and a maximum velocity of 430 cm/sec.

3. Measurements

A prototype transverse doppler current profiler operating at 200 kHz has been used in the Chesapeake Bay near Patuxent river and in the Bear Cut channel adjacent to the Port of Miami. This system used 60 cm total transducer spacing and operated at a pulse repetition rate of 12.5 Hz. It is thus similar to the system proposed above for monitoring harbor currents.

Figure 4 shows a plot of mean flow speed as measured by the transverse DCP in Chesapeake Bay versus measurements by a mechanical VMCM. The agreement is good; much of the disparity is probably due to flow inhomogeneities and the physical separation of the VMCM from the DCP sampling volume. The VMCM averaging time was five minutes, whereas the DCP velocity estimate was made from 1024 pulses or 80 seconds of data using a covariance algorithm [1]. Platform motion prevented reliable estimates of the spectra with the DCP.

Figure 5 is a waterfall plot of doppler spectra versus range measured in Bear Cut. The spectra have been zeroed when the energy was below a threshold to enhance the peaks in the velocity spectra. The lines of constant velocity curve in accordance with equation (6). The system was mounted at the end of a pier at the edge of Bear Cut and looked horizontally toward

Figure 4. Transverse DCP measurements of current in Chesapeake Bay versus mechanical VMCM measurements.

Figure 5. Waterfall plot of thresholded doppler spectra measured with the DCP in Bear Cut.

the channel so that strong returns from the surface and bottom causes the spectra to "wipe out" at the ranges where velocity peaks are absent. Note also the occasional peak at large negative velocity. These may be due to fish or other active swimmers. This illustrates an advantage of systems that give access to the doppler spectrum; spurious signals due to discrete fast moving targets can be identified and eliminated. Note the aliased energy at range gate 5 near the negative Nyquist frequency.

The signals from this experimental DCP were down converted to 5 kHz and recorded on analog tape. These tapes were played back, digitized using a PDP 11/40 and the spectra were computed on a UNIVAC 1108. Best results were obtained when the acoustic signals were processed linearly and not subject to limiting. The minimum between pulse time was limited by returns from multiple surface and bottom reflections to about three times the surface-bottom round trip travel time. Possibly a slow (pulse rate) random sequence would cancel the multiples and permit operation at a higher pulse rate.

4. Summary and Conclusions

A transverse DCP uses a combination of laser velocimeter geometry with doppler radar processing. Previously described DCP systems have either a poor range resolution/velocity variance tradeoff, or an unfavorable maximum range-maximum velocity product. These limits are determined solely by the operating frequency. DCP systems using transverse doppler avoid this problem because the maximum range-maximum velocity product is a function of the receiver transducer spacing as well as the frequency. By judicious choice of operating frequency and transducer geometry, the designer can produce a system optimized for a given water depth and flow velocity. Many potential DCP applications become feasible that were at best marginally possible with previous systems.

A prototype system measured velocity profiles in 17 meters of water with 40 centimeter range resolution and centimeter/second velocity uncertainty after a few minutes of averaging. Transverse doppler current profilers are a practical technology both for real time current monitoring in shipping channels and for ocean science research. Commercial doppler profilers (e.g., Ametek-Straza) suffer from poor range resolution/velocity variance tradeoff; other experimental systems (e.g., Lhermitte [2]) exhibit a small maximum range-maximum velocity product. Use of transverse doppler greatly eases these limitations.

Figure 6. Profiles of flow indicated by position of doppler spectra peaks; individual boxes for each time are ± 100 cm/sec wide.

Velocity profiles such as shown in Figure 6 are produced from 80 seconds of data using standard spectral estimation techniques. Processing time is only about two minutes on a UNIVAC 1108, so that a mini-computer with an FFT array processor could produce profiles in near real time. The present transverse DCP could be easily packaged with a mini-computer to produce a system suitable for real time current monitoring. This DCP would be limited to dry environments with available AC power so that development of a transverse DCP for unattended current measurement would require a large development effort to repack the system.

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